

ISic0007

Construction of fortification works under Sextus Pompeius by L. Plinius Rufus

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

limestone (perhaps local)

Object

slab

Editor

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Principal Contributor

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Contributors

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Autopsy

2015-11-12

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

Found during construction work for the Baglio Anselmi

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo archeologico
regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 42 cm

Width 134 cm

Depth 15 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. \hat{M} ag (no) Pompeio \hat{M} ag (ni) f (ilio) · Pio imp (eratore) augu r̂e
2. co (n) s (ule) · desig (nato) portam et turres
3. L (ucius) · Plinius · L (uci) · f (ilius) Rufus · leg (atus) · pro · pr (aetore) · pr (aetor) · des (ignatus) · f (aciendum) · c (uravit) ·

Apparatus

Translation (en)

When Magnus Pompeius, son of Magnus, Pius Imperator, was Augur and Consul designate, Lucius Plinius

Rufus, son of Lucius, Legatus Propraetore and Praetor designate saw to the construction of the Gate and Towers

Commentary

Cf. Appian, BC 5.98. L. Plinius Rufus subsequently defected to Octavian and

seized Messana. The inscription provides important evidence for Sextus Pompeius' nomenclature and offices after 39 BC.

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